

CARDIOCARE platform and risk stratification models: A beyond the state of the art approach for the management of elderly multimorbid patients with breast cancer therapy induced cardiac toxicity

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Abstract— Breast cancer (BC) is the most common cancer in women in Europe and worldwide, with a high prevalence in middle-aged and older women. The last years, the evolution in the existing treatment approaches have contributed to improved clinical outcomes and survival rates. Nevertheless, BC therapy-related cardiotoxicity, poses a severe impact in the short- and long-term quality of life (QoL) and associated survival of the BC patients. This study demonstrates how the CARDIOCARE platform and the developed risk stratification model provides the healthcare professionals with a valuable tool for effectively managing BC patients, preventing treatment induced cardiotoxicity and improving their QoL. This is accomplished through the integration of multi-source patient- specific data, data from patient-oriented mobile applications and wearable sensors, and by the employment of beyond the state of the art data mining and machine learning approaches.

I. INTRODUCTION

The advancements in early breast cancer (BC) detection and therapy have significantly transformed the natural course of many cancer types into chronic diseases. The reduction in the cancer mortality rates, which is estimated to account for

more than 22 million cancer survivors by 2026 and approximately two-thirds of all cancer survivors will be older than 65 years [1], poses several challenges on how cancer management could be improved. In fact, this improved cancer survival has been compromised by the short, or long-term collateral complications raised by the established cancer therapies. Among the most devastating BC treatment side effects, cardiotoxicity is a major cause of co-morbidity and mortality, further affecting their physical, psychological, social status and QoL [2].

Cardiotoxicity appears in the early or late phases of disease continuum and can manifest in various ways, including abnormalities in heart function to heart failure. Indeed, cardiomyopathy and heart failure, identified as left ventricular dysfunction, represent two prevalent clinical presentations of cardiotoxic adverse effects triggered by cancer treatment [4]. Nonetheless, cardiotoxicity resulting from cancer therapy can present itself in various other ways, such as hypertension, arrhythmias, valvular issues, and coronary artery disease. Cardiotoxicity can emerge at various time intervals and is categorized into three types: acute (during therapy), early

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progressive (within one year of therapy), and late progressive cardiotoxicity (beyond one year of therapy). [5]. Modern cancer treatments, including chemotherapy (anthracyclines, alkylating agents) and monoclonal antibodies, have been linked to an elevated risk of cardiotoxicity. [6]. In Europe, where 3 to 4 million cancer cases are diagnosed annually, BC is the most prevalent type, with 523,000 new cases reported in 2018 [7]. Consequently, there exists a heightened risk of therapy-related complications in BC patients. Notably, these patients undergoing treatment have been a focal point of extensive research, as cardiotoxicity frequently impacts them, leading to reduced life expectancy and diminished QoL [8].

This study introduces an advanced interdisciplinary platform and a risk stratification model, created within the CARDIOCARE project [9], aiming to manage elderly multimorbid patients experiencing cardiac toxicity induced by BC therapy (Figure xx). The novelty of CARDIOCARE lies in its comprehensive approach to BC patient management, incorporating a patient-centric eHealth mobile application and wearable sensors. Additionally, it utilizes a large dataset of both retrospective and prospective clinical data, and leverages sophisticated data mining and machine learning techniques to develop an innovative risk stratification model for QoL.

Figure 1. : Overall concept of CARDIOCARE in relation to cardiotoxicity disease continuum

II. METHODOLOGY

A. CARDIOCARE dataset

Throughout the project's duration, retrospective data from 1560 BC patients and prospective data from 750 patients are being collected.

The retrospective dataset encompasses information from the following: (i) Cardiac imaging and biomarker data, (ii) Blood examination data, (iii) Breast imaging data, (iv) Tissue data, (v) Psycho-markers data, (vi) QoL data. The retrospective data collection involves five clinical centers: the European Institute of Oncology (IEO), the Bank of Cyprus Oncology Centre (BOCOC), the Karolinska University Hospital (KSBC), the National and Kapodistrian University of Athens (NKUA), and the University of Ioannina (UOI).

At present, cardio-oncology guidelines advise incorporating regular examinations, electrocardiograms (ECGs), echocardiograms, circulating biomarkers (such as Troponin I and B-type natriuretic peptide), and a comprehensive

evaluation of the intrinsic capacity of individuals (as per the Integrated Care for Older People - ICOPE guidelines [10]) into a standard follow-up protocol. This approach aims to establish best practices for managing elderly BC patients who are at risk of experiencing cardiotoxic adverse effects. From this standpoint, the CARDIOCARE platform, in conjunction with biological data, is monitoring psychological, emotional, and functional information to serve as informative markers for assessing the risk of cardiotoxicity. The CARDIOCARE prospective clinical study incorporates various procedures, including clinical assessments, genomic analysis, biochemical evaluations, and imaging (echocardiography and mammography). Additionally, health status is continuously monitored through sensor technology, and the CARDIOCARE mobile application is utilized as part of the study.

The prospective clinical study is conducted across six recruitment centers in Europe: IEO, BOCOC, KSBC, UOI, NKUA, and Onkoloski Institut Ljubljana (IOL) [11]. During the 12-month recruitment period, the targeted number of enrolled patients per clinical center is as follows: (i) IEO: 125 patients, (ii) BOCOC: 120 patients, (iii) KSBC: 125 patients, (iv) UOI: 60 patients, (v) NKUA: 195 patients, and (vi) IOL: 125 patients. Out of the total 750 patients, 375 will be assigned to the control group (only monitoring), while the remaining 375 will be placed in the intervention group. The prospective clinical study has just initiated with 16 patients being enrolled from from all clinical centers,

D. Omics - A novel approach to predict cardiotoxicity following cancer treatment

Omics technologies provide a distinctive perspective into the molecular-level mechanisms that could underlie the observed cardiotoxicity resulting from cancer treatment. Genetic variation may account for differences in the onset of cardiotoxicity following treatment, however while numerous genetic biomarkers are recognized for their association with breast cancer predisposition and disease progression, only a limited number are hypothesized to be connected to cardiotoxicity following cancer treatment.

The CARDIOCARE platform combines state-of-the-art omics technologies (genomics, transcriptomics, and metagenomics) to investigate cardiotoxicity in breast cancer (BC) patients. Our primary focus lies on genetic biomarkers within drug metabolism-related genes, which may play a role in influencing variations in drug exposure and subsequently contribute to the development of cardiotoxicity. These biomarkers are anticipated to pave the way for innovative approaches to prognostically identify patients who have an elevated risk of experiencing cardiotoxicity after undergoing chemotherapy. Another omics data modality, miRNA's, offers the opportunity to study the byproducts of activated biological mechanisms of interest. Unlike genetic biomarkers, miRNA biomarkers can indicate whether specific biological mechanisms are active at a particular moment in time. Following an extensive review of the literature on microRNAs as potential biomarkers for chemotherapy-induced cardiotoxicity in breast cancer (BC) patients, we developed a plan to assess multiple candidate miRNAs [13] (Table II). More specifically, the identified panels of informative

microRNA's for chemotherapy-induced cardiotoxicity in BC patients are (i) miR-29a, miR-34a, miR-423, (ii) miR-1, miR-122, miR-499, (iii) miR-17, miR-19a, miR-199, miR-378 and (iv) miR-130a. In CARDIOCARE, an essential factor that may contribute to the variations in cardiotoxicity risk among BC patients undergoing treatment is the gut microbiome. Recent advancements in genetic sequencing have facilitated the targeted identification of genetic regions on the 16s protein of bacteria. As a result, the type of bacteria present in a fecal sample and their relative abundance at various taxonomy levels down to the genus (with high accuracy) and, in some cases, the species level can be determined.

C. Wearable Devices

The patients are continuously monitored using wearable sensors as part of the study. Specifically, 375 patients in the control arm receive two sensor devices and one hand grip dynamometer, which are used in rotation. A smartwatch and a heart zone sensor are employed to collect data on the patients' vital signs and daily activities. The smartwatch records information such as daily activity, step count, heart rate, calories burned, and sleep duration. Meanwhile, the heart zone sensor evaluates the patient's cardiac functionality by monitoring parameters like electrocardiogram (ECG) and Heart Rate Variability (HRV). Additionally, patients are provided with a hand grip dynamometer, as previous studies have indicated a correlation between handgrip strength and cardiac functionality as well as overall psychological status [12].

E. eHealth mobile application

The CARDIOCARE mobile suite comprises two sub-applications: the ePscHeart and the eHealthHeart mobile applications (Figure 2). Patients in the control arm of the clinical study can utilize the ePscHeart mobile application, whereas patients in the intervention arm have access to both the ePscHeart and eHealthHeart mobile applications. The ePscHeart mobile application (Fig. 1), in combination with wearable sensors (smartwatch, heart zone sensor), and the hand grip dynamometer, enables the continuous assessment and monitoring of patients' intrinsic capacity, aiming to enhance their quality of life and support them in self-care and self-management. The application consists of the following modules: (i) Sensors & IoT Module: This module gathers user data from wearable sensors for further analysis. It encompasses the Locomotion Module, which collects and presents data from the smartwatch related to the user's physical activity, and the Vital Condition Module, which collects and displays data from the heart zone sensor concerning the user's heart functionality. (ii) PROMs/PREMs & Questionnaires Module: This module collects and visualizes data from questionnaires. It includes the QoL Module, which evaluates the user's Quality of Life by analyzing their responses from completed questionnaires. The patients are required to complete 14 different questionnaires as part of their assessment for psychological and behavioral status. Some of the included questionnaires are the Anxiety and Depression (PHQ4) questionnaire [14] and the Quality of Life (EORTC-QLQ-30/BR23 [15]) questionnaire. These questionnaires are used to gather comprehensive data about the patients' mental

health, emotional well-being, and overall quality of life. The results from these questionnaires will likely be analyzed to gain insights into the patients' psychological and behavioral conditions

The eHealthHeart mobile application aims to enhance patients' intrinsic capacity by addressing various aspects, such as psychological empowerment, cognitive stimulation, physical activity, vision and hearing status assessment, as well as providing assistance with dietary management and urinary incontinence. This is accomplished through the implementation of the Psychological Support Module, the Cognitive Stimulation Module, the Geriatric Syndromes Assessment Module, the Dietary Nutrition Module, and the Vision and Hearing Module. Furthermore, the application includes the Education and Training Module, which offer valuable resources for psychological and social support, training, and education.

Figure 1. ePscHeart mobile application and main modules.

The Infrastructure

The CARDIOCARE platform (Fig. 3) is created and implemented using a combination of top-performing open-source technologies. At its heart, the platform is designed to facilitate the management of gathered data, allowing for seamless integration of cross-sectional and longitudinal data. Data is being input into the platform through various channels, such as batch upload for retrospective data, streams for sensor data, and manual entry, among other methods. Once the data is collected, harmonization processes are implemented to conform to a standardized data model, with appropriate concept mapping and subject (patient) identification and linking. Subsequently, the harmonized data is stored in specialized repositories within the platform, enabling rapid retrieval and summarization. The platform is implemented on a Kubernetes-enabled cluster of hardware resources, which provides virtualized and containerized monitoring and load balancing services. The processed data can be utilized by a wide range of tools and services, enabling visualization, cohort creation, analytics, and knowledge extraction. This includes the development of data mining and machine learning models, such as the risk stratification model for cardiotoxicity.

Figure 3. CARDIOCARE platform overview.

F. Integrated risk stratification model of cardiotoxicity

The image- and the non-image based risk stratification models are unified in a separate model (integrated risk stratification model of cardiotoxicity), capable of enhancing the early diagnosis and management of cardiotoxicity.

Risk stratification model of cardiotoxicity based on imaging data. The image-based risk stratification model exploits echocardiography images to identify new quantitative imaging biomarkers and signatures predictive of cardiotoxicity and patient response. The design and the implementation stage of the model consists of image processing algorithms suitable for extracting various features (shape, size, text etc.) related to subtle and/or complex predictive signals.

Risk stratification model of cardiotoxicity based on non-imaging data. Using non-imaging data, the application of machine learning techniques allows the development of a risk prediction model for predicting cardiotoxicity. Specifically, the non-imaging data include Electronic Health Records, lab tests, circulating biomarkers (e.g Troponins, BNP) and other data coming from the mobile applications (psychomarkers, questionnaires, physical activity, nutrition, etc). Omics biomarkers (SNPs, miRNAs, gut microbiome) are also included as an additional input.

G. Conclusion

In this study, CARDIOCARE, an integrated platform, for the management of elderly multimorbid patients with BC therapy induced cardiac toxicity, has been presented. To the best of our knowledge, such a holistic approach for stratifying the risk of cardiotoxicity in BC patients, integrating patient-specific data, data from eHealth applications and wearable devices, and data mining and machine learning approaches is not existing, an innovation expected to be validated with records from 1560 retrospective and 750 prospective BC patients in 6 clinical centers.

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